

Meta-heuristics Feature Selection with Pre-trained CNN for Endoscopic Image Classification

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Abstract—The Gastrointestinal (GI) tract, a crucial part of the body, is a common site for cancer-related mortality globally. Early detection through regular screening is essential for identifying abnormalities and preventing serious health complications. While computer-aided diagnosis systems have shown promise in assisting medical professionals, the computational demands of deep learning models for image classification present hurdles to widespread adoption. To address these challenges, we propose a novel approach that combines manual feature selection and classification using traditional machine learning models. By leveraging domain expertise and efficient feature selection techniques, we aim to reduce the computational burden associated with deep learning while maintaining high classification accuracy. In this study, we utilize the Hyperkvasir Dataset, comprising 10662 endoscopic images spanning 23 classes. Our methodology integrates cutting-edge convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures for feature extraction. Following the feature extraction, we used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to reduce dimension. Additionally, we explore different methods for selecting the most relevant features, such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Chi Square test, and ANOVA. Among these methods, combining Densenet121 with PSO and SVM achieves the highest accuracy of 87

Index Terms—Meta-heuristics, Genetic Algorithm, PSO, Optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

The gastrointestinal (GI) tract, a crucial element of human anatomy, serves as a conduit for food digestion and nutrient absorption, spanning from the mouth to the anus. This intricate system comprises two primary segments: the upper GI tract, encompassing the passage from the mouth to the duodenum, and the lower GI tract, extending from the small intestine to the anus. Within the upper GI tract, the process of digestion commences as ingested food is broken down by gastric acids and enzymes before being transported to the lower GI tract for further processing and absorption.

Despite its vital role in maintaining physiological balance, the GI tract is vulnerable to a myriad of medical conditions that can profoundly impact health and well-being. These include gastrointestinal diseases, tissue inflammations, and the development of abnormal growths, such as polyps, along the digestive tract. These abnormalities may manifest as ulcers, sores, or, in more severe cases, malignant tumors, necessitating thorough examination and diagnosis by medical professionals.

Endoscopic procedures, such as colonoscopy and wireless capsule endoscopy, have revolutionized the diagnosis and treatment of GI disorders by providing direct visualization

of the GI tract's internal structures. However, manual examination of endoscopic images remains a labor-intensive and time-consuming process, requiring skilled expertise to identify and classify abnormalities accurately. Moreover, there is a worldwide shortage of healthcare professionals. In Bangladesh a single doctor is responsible for handling 1901 patients [1]. An automated endoscopy screening and examination systems would be beneficial to assist the endoscopists and reduce the labor and time for endoscopy.

Recently, the field of medical image classification has witnessed significant advancements, with computer vision and artificial intelligence (AI) playing pivotal roles in automating the analysis of endoscopic images. Computational endoscopic image analysis typically involves multiple stages, including pathology detection, classification, localization, and segmentation, enabling precise diagnosis and treatment planning. Several image-based AI methods were proposed for autonomous endoscopy screening and examination. However these methods mainly focus on detecting specific anomalies or abnormalities from lower or upper GI tracts. Majority of these methods were proposed for detecting polyps [2]–[11]

Our research aims to contribute to this burgeoning field by proposing an automatic deep-learning-based approach for the classification of different GI diseases from endoscopic images. By leveraging advanced learning algorithms and traditional machine learning, we aim to develop a scalable and efficient system for GI pathology detection. Deep learning models tend to achieve higher accuracy when trained using a large dataset; however in the absence of sufficient train data these models become over-fitted and lack accuracy and robustness. On the contrary, traditional machine learning models can achieve sufficient accuracy when trained using comparatively smaller dataset compared to the deep learning techniques [12], [13]. However, when the number of classes increase these traditional techniques fail to achieve adequate accuracy due to the data limitation. Therefore, in this study, we proposed a cascaded network in which we combined the strength of pre-trained deep learning model's features extraction and traditional machine learning model's classification from limited data [14]. This approach invokes pre-trained weights of deep learning models which involves no learnable parameters. The traditional machine learning based classifiers have only a few parameters. Thus the proposed method is light weight and can be trained using a small dataset to achieve adequate accuracy.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the field of gastrointestinal diagnosis, recent developments in deep learning have led to novel methods for improving the accuracy of detecting and classifying findings, aiming to enable early diagnosis and treatment.

Rajab et al. investigates the efficacy and efficiency of advanced genetic data feature selection and classification algorithms for diagnosing colon cancer. The proposed research adopts a three-phase approach, evaluating feature selection and classification algorithms separately before examining their combined performance. Results reveal that the PSO algorithm excels in feature selection, identifying 29 genes relevant to colon cancer diagnosis, while the SVM algorithm demonstrates superior classification accuracy, achieving nearly 86%. Moreover, the combined use of PSO and SVM exhibits the highest accuracy and performance, significantly outperforming other algorithms and exhibiting faster computational efficiency, with an accuracy rate of 94% [1]. The proposed work aims to implement deep transfer learning for classifying GI diseases using endoscopic images. The dataset consists of 5542 endoscopic images collected from Kvasir and Hyper-Kvasir. Preprocessing steps, including data cleaning, standardization, and augmentation, are conducted to enhance model performance and mitigate overfitting. Pretrained ResNet50 achieves promising results. Comparative analysis against ResNet18 and ResNet34 models reveals superior performance, with the proposed model achieving an average accuracy of 94% [2]. The proposed study aims to employ machine learning techniques, specifically AlexNet, to precisely classify upper GI organ images obtained from routine EGD procedures. A retrospective collection of 85,246 raw upper GI endoscopic images from 441 patients with gastric cancer was assembled, manually classified into 14 distinct categories representing various endoscopic scenarios. The AlexNet framework was trained on 49,174 datasets and validated using an independent dataset of 36,072 images. Results indicated high accuracy rates, with the training and validation datasets achieving accuracies of 0.993 and 0.965, respectively [3]. The study addresses the critical need for automated recognition of GI tract abnormalities in endoscopic images using CNNs. The study used publicly available Kvasir dataset categorized into eight distinct classes, aiming to enhance diagnostic accuracy in GI tract pathology identification. Two state-of-the-art CNN architectures, ResNet50 and DenseNet121, are fine-tuned on the Kvasir dataset to develop robust recognition models. Evaluation on a test set, consisting of 75 images per class demonstrates promising results, with the dense model achieving an accuracy of 86.9% and the residual model achieving 87.8% [4]. Zeng et al. introduces a transfer learning model to classify enteroscopy images for detecting ulcerative proctitis. With a dataset of 1450 endoscopic images, a multi-model fusion network combining Xception, ResNet, and DenseNet achieves high performance, with an accuracy of 97.93%, sensitivity of 99%, and specificity of 99% [5]. He et al. proposes a hybrid loss function to stabilize model training due to low

inter-class variability. For detection tasks, ResNet-152 and MobileNetV3 architectures are used, while Cascade Mask R-CNN is explored for segmentation. Results are evaluated on the HyperKvasir and EndoTect test datasets [6]. This study introduces a deep learning-based hybrid stacking ensemble approach to enhance the detection and classification of GI system findings. The first level employs three new CNN models with 5-fold cross-validation to obtain predictions, while a machine learning classifier at the second level integrates these predictions to reach the final classification. Stacking ensemble models demonstrate superior performance, achieving 98.42% accuracy and 98.19% MCC on the KvasirV2 dataset and 98.53% accuracy and 98.39% MCC on the HyperKvasir dataset[7].

III. METHODOLOGY

In this study, we initiated our methodology by applying deep learning models. Before training the modeling we checked the quality of the images to ensure that only good quality images are used for training. In this study, the focus quality of the images were evaluated using Yagi et al. [17] method and artifacts were detected using Rubina et al. method [18]

A. Deep Learning Model

In this study we used two deep learning models namely, ResNet50 and DenseNet121. These models were trained using pre-existing data and analyzed carefully to find any patterns or insights ResNet50 and DenseNet121. Pretrained weights were utilized and trained over 50 epochs, followed by meticulous analysis of the generated graphs and results to discern patterns and insights.

B. Traditional Machine Learning Model

Subsequently, the focus shifted to the implementation of traditional machine learning models, namely Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), chosen for their suitability to our objectives. ResNet50 and DenseNet121 served as backbone feature extractors, with features extracted from the deep learning models and applied across various traditional machine learning algorithms

C. Feature Selection Techniques

To fine-tune the traditional machine learning models, grid search using Optuna was conducted to determine optimal hyperparameters. Prior to applying the computationally intensive Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed to reduce dimensionality and streamline the search process. Additionally, three distinct feature selection techniques, such as ANOVA and Chi Square test, to improve how well our data was classified.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section depicts various simulation results of the applied deep learning and traditional machine learning techniques of the proposed metaheuristics approach. Table I shows the performance of deep learning models. Both models were train upto 50 epochs.

TABLE I: Deep Learning Model Performance

DL Model	Optimizer	Epoch	Accuracy
Resnet50	Adam	50	79%
Densenet121	Adam	50	82%

Table II shows the accuracy of several deep learning model as feature extractor and classification using traditional machine learning models. It is visible from the table that Resnet50 as feature extractor and SVM as classification model performs best among all of the traditional machine learning models.

TABLE II: Accuracy of Traditional Machine Learning Model without Feature Selection.

Feature Extractor	ML Model	Accuracy
Resnet50	SVM	83%
	RF	75%
	KNN	72%
Densenet121	SVM	53%
	RF	43%
	KNN	36%

In Table III, we observe the accuracy results of different combinations of deep learning models acting as feature extractors and traditional machine learning models for classification. Notably, when using DenseNet121 and ResNet50 as feature extractors alongside Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), they exhibit the highest accuracy scores. Additionally, Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Random Forest (RF) emerge as top-performing classification models, outperforming other feature selection techniques. This underscores the effectiveness of PSO in enhancing the performance of feature extraction and the notable accuracy achieved by SVM and RF in classification tasks.

TABLE III: Accuracy and F1-score of Traditional Machine Learning Models with Feature Selection Techniques

Feature Extractor	Feature Selection	ML Model	Accuracy
Resnet50	ANOVA	SVM	83%
		RF	74%
	PSO	SVM	86%
		RF	75%
	Chi Square	SVM	85%
		RF	78%
Densenet121	ANOVA	SVM	47%
		RF	39%
	PSO	SVM	87%
		RF	75%
	Chi Square	SVM	45%
		RF	36%

Figure 1 illustrates the ROC curves for ResNet50 and Densenet121 model after training for 50 epochs.

Figure 2 illustrates the ROC curves for ResNet50 with SVM, RF, and KNN, without using any feature selection techniques. It is evident from the figure that ResNet50

when combined with SVM as the classification algorithm achieves the highest performance compared to the other two traditional machine learning models.

(a) Densenet121

(b) Resnet50

Fig. 1: ROC curves for Resnet50 and Densenet121 Model

Figure 3 displays the ROC curves for Densenet121 with SVM, RF, and KNN, without the application of any feature selection techniques.

Figure 4 illustrates the ROC curves for Resnet50 with Chi Square feature selection, while Figure 5 illustrates the ROC curves for Resnet50 with ANOVA feature selection.

Figure 6 illustrates the ROC curves for Resnet50 with feature selection conducted through PCA (Principal Component Analysis) for dimensionality reduction and PSO (Particle Swarm Optimization) for feature selection. Similarly, in Figure 7, the ROC curves for Densenet121 are depicted, employing the same feature selection techniques. PCA is utilized to reduce the dimensionality of the feature space, which aids in simplifying the complexity of the model while retaining the essential information. PSO, on the other hand, serves as a feature selection method that optimizes the selection of relevant features for classification tasks. The choice of PSO for feature selection is motivated by its ability to efficiently explore the search space and find optimal subsets of features, thereby enhancing the performance of the classification model.

Figure 7 illustrates the Confusion Matrix for Resnet50 without feature selection technique,

Figure 9 illustrates the Confusion Matrix for Densenet121 without feature selection.

(a) SVM

(b) RF

(c) KNN

(a) SVM

(b) RF

(c) KNN

Fig. 2: ROC curves without feature selection for Resnet50 with SVM, RF, and KNN

Fig. 3: ROC curves for Densenet121 with SVM, RF, and KNN

Figure 9 displays the confusion matrix of the two selected DL models, illustrating their overall accuracy. Figure 10 shows the confusion matrix of the Resnet50 model with ANOVA feature Selection Technique for both SVM and RF model.

V. CONCLUSION

The GI tract remains a significant area of concern for global health due to its association with cancer-related mortality. Early detection through regular screening is imperative to mitigate potential health risks associated with abnormalities. While computer-aided diagnosis systems hold promise in assisting medical professionals, the computational demands of deep learning models pose challenges for widespread adoption. To address these obstacles, we propose an approach that integrates

manual feature selection and classification using traditional machine learning models. By using domain expertise and employing efficient feature selection techniques, our method aims to alleviate the computational burden associated with deep learning, while still achieving high classification accuracy. Our study, conducted on the Hyperkvasir Dataset comprising 10662 endoscopic images across 23 classes, utilizes state-of-the-art CNN architectures for feature extraction. Following feature extraction, PCA is used to reduce dimensionality. Additionally, we explore various feature selection methods, including PSO, Chi Square test, and ANOVA, to identify the most relevant features. Notably, our results demonstrate that combining Densenet121 with PSO and SVM yields the highest accuracy of 87

(a) Chi Square + SVM

(b) Chi Square + RF

(a) PCA + PSO + SVM

(b) PCA + PSO + RF

Fig. 4: Chi Square test using Resnet50 Feature Extractor

Fig. 6: ROC Curve of Resnet50 model with PSO feature Selection Technique

(a) ANOVA + SVM

(b) ANOVA + RF

(a) PCA + PSO + SVM

(b) PCA + PSO + RF

Fig. 5: ANOVA test using Resnet50 Feature Extractor

Fig. 7: ROC Curve of Densenet121 model with PSO feature Selection Technique

(a) Resnet50 + SVM

(b) Resnet50 + RF

(c) Resnet50 + SVM

(a) Densenet121 + SVM

(b) Densenet121 + RF

(c) Densent121 + KNN

Fig. 8: Confusion Matrix for Resnet50 with ANOVA, Chi Square, and without feature selection

Fig. 9: Confusion Matrix for Densenet121 without feature selection

(a) Resnet50

(b) Densenet121

Fig. 10: Confusion Matrix of Resnet50 and Densenet121 model

(a) ANOVA + SVM

(b) ANOVA + RF

Fig. 11: Confusion Matrix of Resnet50 model with ANOVA feature Selection Technique

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